

TO THE THEORY OF METALANGUAGE OF TRANSLATION AND
TRANSLATOLOGY

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The article attempts to develop the theory of the metalanguage of translation and translatology, which is replete with private linguistic terms and expressions on the theory and practice of translation, in particular, it has developed and proposed a system of terms and notions based on the word "translation" and translation related phenomena and (their) possible derivatives, which allowed the author to create whole paradigm of such unified notions and terms of a general translation character (as "translate" and its derivatives "translating, translated translatology, translatalogist, translatalogical, translatalogically, translator, translate, translate (meaning "транслат"), as well as such contiguous notions and terms as "transliteration, transcription, transferences, transformations", etc., which served as the basis for the creation of the metalanguage of translatology. Based on the notion and term of a "translate" the authors have developed and proposed the taxonomy of translation units as to the levels of language hierarchy: fono-translate, morpho-translate, morpho-phonotranslate: lekso-translate, syntakso-translate, phraseo-translate, texto-translate (discourso-translate), speech realizations of which, following O.Kade, are conditionally termed as : fono-translate, morpho-translate, morpho-phonotranslate, lexo-translate, syntaxo-translate (represented by phrase-translate and sentence-translate) phraseo-translate and texto-translate. (discourso-translate)

Translation science - translation studies (or as it is also fashionably called In general Linguistics terms as “translatology”) has a long tradition, and translation is as ancient as the language itself and at present it continuously and successfully develops. Despite the undoubted progress in this direction, there are still a lot of unresolved and topical issues of the science of translation, among which we can mention the problem of the unification of notions, terms, units, theory and metalanguage of translation, which general theory and practice of translation is so badly in need of (Salomov 1966;1978; Каде 1966; Schweitzer 1973, 1984, 1988; Retzker 1974; Barkhudarov 1975; Krupnov 1976; Minyar-Beloruchev 1976, 1980; Nida 1975; Sawory 1978; Chernov 1979; Shiryaev 1979; Vlachov, Florin 1980; Komissarov 1980, 1989; Tarjima nazariyasi asoslari1983; Fedorov 1985; Hertman 1985; Lilova 1985; Chernov 1987 etc.).

Our observations on translation research show that many significant and valuable results have been achieved in the theory and practice of translation by researchers and scholars , but the question of the *unit* of translation, unification of metaconcepts, metaterms, metatheory and the metalanguage of translation as an object of independent research has not been carried out yet. However, further development of translation science as a whole, in our opinion, in many respects depends on the solution of this topical and cardinal issue.

If one comes closer to the analysis of special literature on the theory and practice of translation, one can see that there are quite a few such multilingual notions and terms meaning either the process of translation itself, or the result of this process as Russian “перевод”, Uzbek “таржима”, English “translation”, German “übersetzung”, French “traduction or traduzione”, etc.

In order to facilitate the same understanding and use of the above multilingual notions and terms from the point of view of the general theory and practice of translation, and in order to unify them, it is advisable to conditionally use the general term “translate” (which means “переводить” or “переносить” in Russian) and to derive from it a whole paradigm of such notions and terms of

general translation character as translatology, translologist, translator, translately, translate¹, including even such contiguous notions and terms as “transliteration, transcription, transference, transfer, transformation”, etc.

Below we will try to characterize each of the above given unified notions and terms and disclose their meanings: 1) *translatology* is the science of translation (i.e. translation science), which investigates all kinds of translations (both oral (interpretation) and written translations and has the following sections: the history of translation and translation studies, introduction to the theory and practice of translation, theory and practice of translation, translation criticism; 2) *translator* is a specialist of translation, who translates or interprets different materials from one language into the other; 3) *translateme* is a unit of translation (such as a phoneme, morpheme, morphophoneme, lexeme, syntaxeme (phraseme, sentenceme) phraseoeme and texteme (discourseme); 4) *translate* is the realization of the emic unit “translateme” in speech as an ethic unit; 5) *transliteration* is one of the ways of translating strictly carried out within the framework of phonemes serving as translatelys, for example, when translating onomastic units (anthroponyms, toponyms, onomatopoeic means (onomatopoeemes) and realememes); 6) *transcription* is a translation carried out by preserving the exact pronunciation of the translately, for example, “know-how” and “realeme” such as “sunnat, ramazan, iftorlik, sakharlik, golf, coffee, football, basketball, tennis”, etc.); 7) *transference* is a translation or transfer of meaning from one language into another; 8) *transformation* is a translation or transform of meaning from one language into another;

¹For detailed information on “translateme” and its types in see: Hoshimov G.M. Lectures on Simultaneous Interpretation Andizhan – 2003, pp.24-29; Hoshimov G.M., Hoshimov A.G, Hoshimov M. G. Simultaneous translation and sign factor of source language//Actual problems of translatology, Andizhan, 2008, –Matbaa, pp.194-196: For comparative information on “translateme” and «транслат» see: Каде О. . Субъективные и объективные факторы в процессе перевода»,. 1964, 47; See also: Tyulenev S. V. Theory of translation. Uchebnoe posobie: 2004 Izdatelstvo: Gardariki, 336 c.

Based on the aforesaid, it may be concluded that depending on language units representing various levels of language hierarchy the above translates can be conditionally designated by the following unified terms:

- 1) phono-translateme (expressed by a phoneme);
- 2) morpho-translateme (expressed by a morpheme);
- 3) morphophono-translateme (expressed by morphophoneme);
- 4) lexo-translateme (expressed by a lexeme);
- 5) syntaxo-translateme (expressed by the syntaxeme of two subtypes):
 - a) phrase-translateme (expressed by a phrase);
 - b) sentenco-translateme expressed by sentenceme);
- 6) phraseo-translateme (expressed by a phraseoeme - phraseological unit);
- 7) texto-translateme (discoursio-translateme) (expressed by texteme /discourseme/).

Hence, the speech realizations of the above translates can be conditionally designated as follows:

- 1) phono-translate² (expressed by a phoneme);
- 2) morpho-translate (expressed by a morpheme);
- 3) morpho-phonotranslate (expressed by a morphophoneme);
- 4) lexo-translate (expressed by a lexeme);
- 5) syntaxo-translate (translate expressed by syntaxeme of two subtypes):
 - a) phrase-translate (expressed by a phraseme);
 - b) sentenco-translate (expressed by sentenceme);
- 6) phraseo-translate (expressed by phraseoeme - phraseological unit);
- 7) texto-translate (discoursio-translate) (expressed texteme (discourseme)).

The unified apparatus of the metanotions, metaterms and, in general, of the metalanguage of translation proposed by us for the first time in translatology does not contradict the current tendencies of linguistic (more precisely, translational)

² О «транслате» как единице перевода см.: Каде О. Субъективные и объективные факторы в процессе перевода»,. 1964, 47

term creation, coming from their Latino-Greek origins, as it creates convenience and provides the same - unified understanding and use of translates by translators and translatoologists and contributes to development of the general theory and practice of translation.

Problems of correlation of the above-mentioned translates as language units and translates as their immediate realizations of the former and their ability to interchanges in the context of their isomorphism and allomorphism by virtue of the current language and speech norms in practical translation, as well as questions of terminological character will be revealed in detail and accordingly illustrated in the report.

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